

Emotional Intelligence in Teaching of College Teachers

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321 - 4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Ramachandran, P
& Pushpa Veni, K.
“Emotional Intelligence
in Teaching of College
Teachers.” *Shanlax
International Journal of
Management*, vol. 6,
no. S1, 2019, pp. 48–51.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2590377](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2590377)

Abstract

Teachers are considered as the professional personnel who are involved in the direct student instruction which involves planning; organizing and conducting group activities - students' knowledge, skills, and attitudes develop as predetermined through the educational programmes. Emotional competence and social competence are widely recognized as important components for educational achievement and for lifelong learning. Teachers with high emotional intelligence competencies are optimistic, adaptable, collaborative, confident, authoritative, open, approachable and enthusiastic they have better communication skills, better abilities for conflict resolution and problem-solving, better impulse and self-control and higher self-esteem.

Key words: Emotional intelligence, Teacher's performance, Teaching

Introduction

Emotional intelligence as the ability to understand expressions of emotions in oneself and others, together with making the advantage of emotions in thoughts and actions. A good teacher needs a better understanding of the individual and group motivation and behavior to create a knowledgeable environment that encourages optimistic social interaction, energetic engagement and the enthusiasm to learn. Teachers are regarded as the main pillar of the teaching organization. They also considered as mediators, because through them only the knowledge is passed to the students. They are an effective source of knowledge because they possess the essential skills, knowledge, and talents. Emotional Intelligence involves healthy emotional behavior. It includes various characters such as thinking, finding, managing and expressing feelings. Emotional Intelligence enables the individuals to react at the right place, right time and for the right purpose in the right way.

In the present study, emotional intelligence has been defined as the ability of a person to distinguish and comprehend one's own emotions and those of others and regulate or manage those emotions so as to motivate self and others for achieving specific goals.

Need for the Study

Today we analyze a number of problems among the students. These include maladjustments, delinquencies, emotional disturbances, behavioral problems, criminality, etc. To surmount these problems, emotional literacy is necessary. Teachers with better emotional intelligence communicate the components of emotional intelligence such as confidence, curiosity, intentionality, self-control, relatedness and cooperativeness to the students effectively. The emotionally intelligent teacher creates a safer and more satisfying, caring, and productive school environment. Emotional intelligence is highly useful in the place where interpersonal relationships are being generated – schools, home, workplace, and other organizational settings.

Emotional Intelligence and Teaching

A schooling system is a public system in which tutors and other school faculties cooperate with children in several situations. Exclusively main in education and academic development were experienced by each child is the communication between tutor and scholar. Even more complex and significant is the capability to launch emotional constancy and safety for scholars who may be undergoing the adverse impacts of poverty such as prolonged stress or other social/ emotional shortages.

Many investigators have recommended that certain preliminary courses directing at improving the importance of psychological characters such as emotional intelligence should be integrated with learning courses planned for novice tutor so that it will contribute to educational improvement. Possibly the most actual way to encourage the community and emotional capabilities of pre-service tutor would be for tutor's education to change its main purpose from that of emerging student-tutors mental skills to that of emerging student-tutors affective competencies. One unending problematic area within the tutor's efficacy project is the deficient of attention to the sources of tutor's efficacy and how these work in practice.

ERA predicts lower emotional exhaustion, skill to improve special interactions with students, and a high number of positive reactions, including feelings of success and fulfillment in teaching. Those tutors with high emotional regulation, in other words, who determine a capability to increase their positive feelings and decrease their negative feelings, are more dynamic and effective in the study room.

Important in these four models (ERA, emotional labor, SEC, and REBT) is their association with EI, which, in turn, influences tutor efficiency. Both emotional labor and ERA are means of controlling emotions based on situation and environment influences. In these two models, the involvement of emotional response management by the person fits within sub factors of EI concept (e.g. within "controlling feelings of the ability model).

EI methods and activities provide equally to positive management in the classroom and are shown to be helpful in the description of a person's changes in the tutor's SEC. To this point, EI has been displayed to reduce the impacts of tutor's tension and encourage personal welfare, therefore the viewpoint that EI is essential to the alteration and development of these tutor's efficiency-relevant variables. This showed differences between people with varying stages of emotional management, stress tolerance, and classroom outcomes.

Most of the programs have components aimed in enhancing the teachers' personal well-being and its focus on the self-regulation. Amusingly, most of the components emulate the skills present among individuals with higher EI and are adopted through EI training. Some of the major examples include Rational Emotive Education which is utilized in educational settings to help the teachers in reducing the stress, which regulates their behavior and emotions in handling disruptive students and improvising the overall effectiveness of the study.

Evidence shows that a teacher's self-emotional efficacy has a great impact on the successful implementation of the program. Major attempts to enhance the positive teaching characteristics are created through an array of successful professional development programs and workshops. This ranges from strengthening the content knowledge in various subject areas, enhancing the classroom management skills, improving the pedagogical skills for the instructional support, skill training include personal coping. EI provides an avenue to enhance and augment the teacher efficacy and the associated indicators which describes the term "effective teacher". From the earlier studies of EI programs for the teachers (Emotional Intelligence in the Classroom", a detailed study is initiated by authors with pre-service teachers during the university training program and initial few years of teaching. One of the prior studies suggests that psychologically positive learning is the foundation for both achievement and academic engagement. This fact emphasizes effective teaching demands.

Emotional Intelligence and Teacher's performance

Emotional intelligence is vitally important in all the fields because it speculates victory in all ways of life. The students and teachers have many difficulties in their lives; these difficulties become a major interruption in classrooms across the nations. So that it is very important to develop emotional and social skills by the teacher at the education institution. Because it can have a good academic achievement not only during the year they taught but during the years that follow as well. Due to all these reasons, huge importance and needs are required for investigating the emotional intelligence of teacher educators. The positive outcome of achievements, goal achievement, and personal wellbeing builds human development behaviors. Emotional intelligence is key for building this human development behavior. An emotional knowledge program is effective in improving emotional knowledge and the ability of tutors a good tutor needs an understanding of single and group motivation and personality to make an educational surrounding that creates positive social communication, active commitment and the motivation to learn.

Importance in the area of teacher professional growth has increased recently, reflecting an increasing appreciation for the public as the most significant source in the school system, a rising concern in education changes and current importance on accountability and quality assurance in the area of education.

High-quality professional tutors are considered important for effective, high-quality teaching and school success. Specifically, it has been recognized that tutors require continuously developing their professional abilities, extending their knowledge and remaining current with new professional thoughts, advanced technologies, and other improvements.

Emotional intelligence can allow educators to determine previous problems and both exterior as well as struggles, aid them to achieve emotional power and also enhance psychological skills such as thinking and resolution making. Emotional intelligence permits the humans to react to the correct grade, at the correct time for the correct purpose and in the correct way to a different of environmental conditions. Emotional intelligence is equally dependent and vital features of the nature of prospective educators.

Review of Literature

Sunil Trivedi and Arti Shakya (2014) worked on the perspective of the teachers to analyze their Emotional Intelligence in relation to Gender, SES and Caste. The sample size is 300. The study was conducted in B.Ed. Colleges which is affiliated to Bundelkhand University, Jhansi by adopting the semi probability sampling techniques. The results portray a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of both male and female prospective teachers. The prospective teachers fit into GEN category showed a great level of emotional intelligence when compared to the OBC &

SC prospective teachers. The levels of SES of the prospective teachers do not cause any significant difference in emotional intelligence.

Uma Devi and Chitti Babu (2015) investigated the level of emotional intelligence of faculty members in the selected engineering colleges in Kadapa district. A study was being conducted on 240 sample size with 3 diverse types of designations. The tools which are used for analyzing data were the sampling technique and the descriptive statistics. The study identified that happiness and emotionality factors are extremely influencing on faculty members emotional intelligence when compared with the sociability & self-control factors. It is accomplished that the possession of the high emotional Intelligence is much more imperative on managing the emotions and stress at the workplace.

Surya Kumar and Shani (2016) worked on the level of Emotional Intelligence in college teachers having the qualification of the postgraduates, post graduate with NET, M.Phil, and Ph.d. A model was used to establish the EI level in terms of Burnout, which implied that the proposed model was a good fit. SEM technique was used to check the goodness of the model. The sample size of around 500 college teachers from the Coimbatore Municipal Corporation was considered for the research work. The study concluded that Post Graduates have a better level of the mean emotional index when compared to other graduates.

Conclusion

Emotional intelligence helps to build social relationships and managing emotions. The teachers who have better emotional intelligence communicates with the constructive goal in mind and controls his or her emotions carefully more than reacting to the situation on the basis of impulse generated by emotion generated event. This may help to commence some change in the work environment so as to augment the level of emotional intelligence among the teachers at the workplace.

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